

LOCK-INS ANALYSIS

DEVELOPING FOOD VALUE CHAIN TRANSITION PATHWAYS: A STAKEHOLDER-BASED PROCESS

PROJECT
REPORT
D8.2

VALUMICS - UNDERSTANDING FOOD VALUE
CHAINS AND NETWORK DYNAMICS

MARCH 2021

Food Systems Dynamics

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ABOUT

VALUMICS stands for value chain dynamics and is a research project funded by the EU H2020 programme. VALUMICS will enable decision makers to evaluate policy impact on food value chains

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VALUMICS

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Lock-ins analysis

**Developing Food Value Chain transition pathways:
a stakeholder-based process**

Food Systems Dynamics

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

FVC(s) – Food Value Chain(s)
F2F Strategy – Farm to Fork Strategy
WS – Workshop Series

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Recent biophysical scenarios have provided a clear picture of what the European food system should become by 2050 in order to stay within environmental limits (EAT-Lancet Commission, 2019; European Commission COM, 2018; Karlsson et al., 2017; Poux & Aubert, 2018). Although these modelling exercises depict a desirable long-term horizon, they leave completely open the question of *how* to get there – in other words, how supply chains should evolve, which actors will drive the change, and with what specific levers. Yet, radical shifts in production and consumption will require a significant reconfiguration of Food Value Chains (FVCs). This raises challenging economic, social and political considerations that are currently subject to heated debate.

Identifying and characterising FVC “transition pathways” by 2030 is at the heart of VALUMICS Work Package 8. To do so, the VALUMICS team convened a multi-stakeholder dialogue bringing together over 20 stakeholders from the European food system community to help build a policy roadmap for the transformation of the European food system. Between November 2020 and January 2021, representatives from decision-making, business, research and civil society collectively defined the direction of travel and investigated the main obstacles, levers and trade-offs involved. The issues pertaining to three specific value chains (wheat, dairy and protein crops) were discussed in detail. This process helped identify three cross-cutting “lock-ins” currently preventing FVC actors from adopting more sustainable strategies: i) consumer habits; ii) market organisation (competition and trade rules); and iii) the current agricultural policy framework. It also brought to light certain “no regret options” for fostering a more favourable policy framework.

The first section lays out the design of the Workshop Series and the methodology used to garner stakeholders’ inputs into the development of FVC transition pathways. The second part highlights three major policy areas that were identified by participants as representing particularly important obstacles – i.e., “*lock-ins*” - preventing the transformation of FVCs: (i) consumer habits; ii) market organisation (competition and trade rules); and iii) the current agricultural policy framework. It provides suggestions for creating a more favourable policy framework in these areas. Finally, the last part summarizes the transition pathways co-developed during the Workshop Series for three food value chains: (i) wheat, (ii) protein crops and (iii) dairy.¹

¹ The VALUMICS project is as well working on other FVC and further analysis of lock-ins concerning the processed tomato and aquaculture salmon chains. This will be reported on in follow up publications and is not covered by this deliverable report.

INTRODUCTION

The trajectory taken by Europe in the past 50 years has brought our food system to a deadlock. The emergence of large-scale monocultures and the intensification of livestock productions have contributed to unprecedented impacts on the environment, including widespread biodiversity loss and increasing GHG emissions (IPES-Food, 2019). The agri-food sector also faces significant socio-economic challenges, notably marked by the dramatic decline in employment and lagging incomes in the farming sector (farm income currently represent 40% of average EU wages) as well as staggering levels of indebtedness among farmers (European Commission, 2017). These dynamics are strongly interrelated with the prevalence of power asymmetries and unfair trading practices which have been exacerbated by vertical integrations and concentrations at the downstream level of FVCs (European Commission, 2019a). In light of these multiple crises, a drastic change of direction is required to build a food system that both respects planetary boundaries while keeping within the bounds of our economy's social foundations (Raworth, 2017; Rockström et al., 2009).

A number of recent high-level research publications have closely examined the scale of change needed and depict what the European food system should look like by 2050 from a **biophysical perspective** to meet sustainability objectives (EAT-Lancet Commission, 2019; European Commission COM, 2018; Karlsson et al., 2017; Poux & Aubert, 2018). Although these scenarios diverge on a number of aspects, they all point towards common objectives: i) the reduction by at least 50% of food loss and waste; ii) a change in farming practices, especially to reduce the use of inputs (fertiliser and pesticides); iii) and finally, at the heart of the challenge lies the necessity of a **“protein transition”** – that is, a dietary shift to reduce the consumption and production of animal products while increasing plant-based alternatives². This latter issue has found growing resonance in the political agenda, and more specifically in the recent Farm to Fork Strategy which lays out the political framework to accompany the transformation of the European food system (European Commission, 2020b).

Figure 1: Imagining the 2050 food system: biophysical scenarios

² This report does not address the role of aquaculture in sustainable food systems; however, other studies such as the EAT-Lancet seafood report (Troell et al., 2019) have examined the role of seafood within sustainable diets.

While these prospective scenarios paint a clear picture of the 2050 horizon, they fall short of telling us **how we can get there, and more specifically, what sort of changes should take place in food value chains (FVCs) to make the protein transition economically and socially viable.** To this effect, the F2F strategy has emphasised the role of economic actors along FVCs in driving the transition: it notably calls upon voluntary commitments from food companies (including processors, food service operators, retailers, etc.) to put in place more responsible business strategies (soon to be formalised in the “EU Code of conduct for responsible business and marketing practices”). However, beyond the level of individual companies - and the potential limits of voluntary self-regulation -, it has become necessary to think about how such changes in business strategies can be aligned and articulated around larger sectoral reconfigurations.

Indeed, the protein transition poses significant challenges for specific sectors, especially for the livestock and feed industries, as it requires a clear decrease in volumes produced/consumed. From an economic perspective, this begs the question of how these specific FVCs may shift their **strategic orientation** (i.e., from a volume-based approach to a more quality-oriented strategy), and to identify under what social and political conditions this would be financially feasible. In other words, it has become crucial to consider how we may **design viable FVC-specific “transition pathways”** (Geels & Schot, 2007) towards a sustainable food system. Turnheim et al. (2015) have defined transition pathways as “patterns of changes in socio-technical systems unfolding over time that led to new ways of achieving specific societal functions. (They) involve varying degrees of reconfiguration across technologies, supporting infrastructures, business models and production systems, as well as the preferences and behaviour of consumers.”

The development of transition pathways thus seeks to investigate the concrete **operationalisation** of FVC transformation along three complementary dimensions (see Rosenbloom, 2017):

- (i) The biophysical dimension: i.e., changes in material fluxes and environmental footprint
- (ii) The technico-economic dimension: i.e., changes in business models and consequences for value creation/distribution
- (iii) The socio-political dimension: i.e., changes in policies and societal pressures needed to enable these transformations

The following figure showcases the central role of transition pathways in bridging the gap between the current situation and long-term sustainability objectives:

Food Value Chains (FVC) – Theory of Change

Figure 2: Theory of Change

In order to build coherent transition pathways for European FVCs and give voice to those most concerned with creating the future of the European food system, VALUMICS organized a multi-stakeholder dialogue (see below). This report builds upon the workshop discussions and outcomes:

1. **The first section** lays out the design of the Workshop Series and the methodology used to garner stakeholders’ inputs into the development of FVC transition pathways.
2. **The second part** highlights three major policy areas that were identified by participants as representing particularly important obstacles or “lock-ins” preventing the transformation of FVCs: (i) consumer habits; ii) market organisation (competition and trade rules); and iii) the current agricultural policy framework. It provides suggestions for creating a more favourable policy framework in these areas.
3. **Finally, the last part** summarizes the transition pathways co-developed during the Workshop Series for three food value chains: (i) wheat, (ii) dairy and (iii) protein crops.³

³ Two other VALUMICS case studies will be analyzed in terms of transition pathways towards sustainable future scenarios and lock-ins: the aquaculture salmon chain, and the processed tomato chain.

1 THE VALUMICS WORKSHOP SERIES

1.1 GENERAL OBJECTIVES

Between November 2020 and January 2021, VALUMICS convened a multi-stakeholder dialogue with 20+ stakeholders from the European food system community with the overarching aim of **developing a roadmap for the sustainable transformation of food value chains towards 2030**⁴. Over the course of six virtual meetings, representatives from policymaking, businesses, research and civil society were invited to collectively identify and explore the main **obstacles, trade-offs, and levers** towards shifting FVC strategies, while making especially clear socio-economic implications.

The more specific objectives were to:

1. Identify different options for European food value chain transition: **direction of travel** and destination
2. Deep dive into the **transition pathways**: lock-ins, leverage points and roles of different actors are understood and can be acted on
3. Identify commonalities which make policy action “**no regret options**” in terms of scales of impact and trade-offs
4. Build multi-stakeholder trust and **common understanding**, including where there is alignment and divergence between stakeholders

As a general guiding thread, the Workshop Series (WS) was framed around the challenges of a ‘protein transition’. To this end, discussions were particularly structured around **three FVC case studies** of key importance: (i) **dairy**, (ii) **wheat**, and (iii) **protein crops**. These sectoral ‘deep dives’ allowed participants to explore contrasted aspects and challenges of the protein transition since each FVC faces different directions to meet sustainability targets: i.e., the development of the protein crop sector *versus* a reduction in the production of animal products such as dairy, and therefore of animal feed including wheat. FVC transition pathways were developed on the basis of these three case studies by identifying the specific political, economic, social and technological factors to enable a shift in FVC actors’ strategies.

From the onset, the objective was not to strive for collective consensus on the specific path to follow, but to deliberately acknowledge and **explore underlying tensions and dilemmas** (for example, on the place of trade/exports in future FVCs, or on the importance of technology versus socio-political innovations, etc.). This “provocative” framing was critical to move beyond often sterile confrontations between different worldviews and start identifying critical solutions in a productive discussion around the main challenges we face in the next 10 years.

⁴ <https://www.iddri.org/en/publications-and-events/workshop/valumics-workshop-series-transformation-european-food-value-chains>

1.2 CALENDAR AND STRUCTURE

The VALUMICS Workshop Series took place between 6 November 2020 and 12 January 2021 in the midst of a rather momentous political climate for European/international food policy. Indeed, a few months before, the Farm to Fork strategy had been published, setting the ambition for the European food system’s evolution in next decade. The UN Food Systems Summit is also set to occur later in 2021 and a number of Dialogues are being organized in the lead up to it. Finally, the CAP reform is currently in the trilogue phase of negotiation until mid-2021.

In this context, the WS spanned across several weeks and was structured around a total of six sessions: a short kick-off meeting, three half-day workshops, a shorter intermediary touchpoint, and a follow-up meeting. The overall process unfolded as follows:

1. The first workshop helped build common understanding and alignment on the general direction of travel towards a sustainable and fair food system
2. The second workshop and touchpoint explored specific issues within each food value chain and identified key socio-political conditions for change
3. The third workshop helped refine compelling transition pathways and explored implications for collective action

Figure 3: Workshop Series Timeline

Due to the Covid-19 pandemic, the entire process took place virtually, over the online platform Zoom. Despite the conditions, a suite of tools was mobilised to create a **collaborative and productive virtual space** - including Slido, which was used to punctuate meetings with questions and surveys, and a Google Drive space to post all materials and contents related to the workshops. Furthermore, to ensure strong

participant engagement throughout, each meeting was divided between plenary moments and break-out sessions where stakeholders had the opportunity to discuss in smaller groups. These break-out sessions were moderated by VALUMICS organizers, while participants were often asked to report back to the plenary to share the outcomes of each discussion.

Throughout the WS, the organizing team also created a number of **content pieces** to feed the discussions:

- PowerPoint presentations were prepared for each session and provided food for thought and a general framing to guide participants in their reflections and exchanges
- Lock-Ins briefing notes and FVC Case Studies were sent out before the touchpoint as a basis for discussion on the obstacles and levers to the transformation of FVCs
- three 2-pager documents presenting FVC-specific transition pathways were produced before WS3 built upon the workshop discussions

At the end of the process, the key public output of the VALUMICS Workshop Series is a co-owned **Outcome Document** which synthesizes the key messages coming out of the stakeholder discussions. This brief provides a strategic direction for actors within the European food system to meet long-term sustainability targets. It underlines key issues pertaining to specific FVCs and highlights three cross-cutting policy levers/areas of change. Since the final objective is to have participants disseminate this document within their ecosystems, the WS deliberately fostered collective and individual buy-in and ownership of the key messages by asking participants to actively provide feedback and inputs to the document. However, they did not need to fully “endorse” the entirety of the brief’s content (the document itself recognizes that the WS did not always strive for consensus on all aspects of the discussion).

1.3 PARTICIPANTS

The impressive **diversity of participants** that took part in the *VALUMICS Workshop Series* was one of the key features that made this dialogue and its collective dynamic so unique. Indeed, the workshops brought together over 20 stakeholders from a wide variety of positions in the European food system: policymakers at the local level (municipal/regional representatives) and European level (EU Commission), businesses from across food value chains (processors, retailers, etc.), as well as research and civil society organizations. In blending together such an improbable network of participants, the exchanges captured a rich variety of perspectives and created links between actors who do not usually have the opportunity to exchange.

Selection criteria: Aside from the specific position they occupied within the European food system, other key criteria for selecting participants were (i) their influence within and beyond the scope of their particular organization; (ii) their willingness to engage in an open dialogue and acknowledge the tensions and trade-offs concerning the challenges at hand; (iii) and, last but not least, their ability to commit the time and effort to such a time-intensive process.

Limitations: Concerning the representativeness of this group of participants, the only significant shortcoming was the insufficient representation of stakeholders from the producer side. Only one actor – the Deputy Director for the French Federation of Protein and Oilseed Crop Producers - was there to speak of the agricultural sector. Despite having invited a number of farming representatives (CEJA, European Milk Board, COPA-COGECA, etc.), the overlap with the ongoing CAP negotiations prevented them from committing time to the workshop series.

Table 1: Final Participant List

Policy representatives	Sofie Verhoeven	City of Ghent
	Fabien Santini	EC - DG AGRI
	Henk Westhoek	EC - DG SANCO
	Adelma Di Biasio	EC – REA
	Blaga Valentinova Popova	EC – DG GROW
	Natalia Brzezina/Anna Seip	EC - DG AGRI
	Nicola Dall’Olio	Emilia-Romagna Region
Business representatives	Aymeric Olibet	BNP-Paribas Fortis
	Didier Moreau	Danone
	Ole Christensen	Biomar/FEFAC
	Damien François/Anne Meyer	Bjorg Bonnetterre et Cie
	Norbert Reichel	Food-Processing Initiative
	Jan Dörrich	REWE International
	Claude Soudé	FOP
	Nathalie Lecocq	FEDIOL
	Giovanni Sorlini	Filiera Italia

Think tanks	Mariana Nicolau/ Luis Esquivel	CSCP
	Stephanie Wunder	Ecologic
	Francesco Ajena	IPES-Food
Researchers	Philippe Baret/ Clémentine Antier	UCL (Louvain)
	David Barling	University of Hertfordshire
	Tomaso Ferrando	University of Antwerp

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	Antonella Samoggia	University of Bologna
	Luis Esquivel	CSCP
	Gudrun Olafsdottir	University of Iceland
	Ivan Duric	IAMO
	Sigurdur Bogason	University of Iceland
	David Barling	University of Hertfordshire

Figure 4: Screenshot from break-out session

1.4 WORKSHOP DESIGN

1.4.1 KICK-OFF MEETING

The primary objective of this first meeting was to welcome participants to the Workshops Series and allow them to **meet as a new community** so that they could start to get a sense of each other and the value each would bring to the discussions. Beyond that, this introductory session aimed to bring stakeholders to **understand their contribution and commit** to both the WS objectives and to its process, getting to grips with the essential content challenges and the opportunity it presented. To set the stage, the VALUMICS team notably presented the general framing of the series within the context of the F2F strategy and the growing political momentum and ambition around the question of food system sustainability. It pointed towards a number of **major dilemmas to collectively overcome**:

- How will food chains transform? With what impacts? ... to be coherent with agreed conditions (F2F)
- Can we bridge the gap(s) between science, societal demands, businesses and policy to come out with innovative propositions at the EU level?
- Opposite views exist on what is needed, but with little evidence to move beyond this opposition

The kick-off meeting also provided an opportunity to launch the virtual Collaborative Written Conversation which took place until Workshop#1 – as described below.

1.4.2 COLLABORATIVE WRITTEN CONVERSATION

In order to move towards some common understanding of the challenges at hand, participants were invited to answer four intentionally provocative questions via a Google Form questionnaire. Each question was prefaced with a short contextualisation paragraph. The objective of this exercise was to **bring to light key areas of existing divergence and convergence in the group**.

1. **FVCs for sustainable food systems: what is at stake?** Several food chain actors contend that most challenges our food system faces can be tackled relying first and foremost on technological and scientific innovations. Would you agree with this view? If yes, why? If not, what alternatives do you see to transform food value chains so that they contribute to a more sustainable and fairer food system?
2. **Promoting healthy and sustainable diets:** In your view, should animal protein consumption decrease in Europe and, if so, to what extent? What type(s) of animal protein (beef, poultry, dairy, fish...) should be prioritised as part of a sustainable diet?
3. **Reconfigurations of production and trade:** To what extent should a reduction in animal protein consumption translate into a reduction in animal protein production within Europe? In other words, what should be the contribution of

European producers to the provision of sustainable animal proteins to the rest of the world?

4. **Transforming food value chains:** Who are the value chain actors that should drive the change, and what are the best strategies to do so?

Overall, there was a broad agreement among participants on the importance of reducing animal protein consumption within the EU; however, maintaining a sufficient level of production to supply the world with sustainable animal proteins was supported by a few stakeholders (i.e., EU as a provider of climate-efficient animal products), which pointed to contrasted visions regarding the scale of reduction needed in EU livestock production. Furthermore, although most actors believed that technological changes would play a role in the transition, many of them pointed out that institutional, social and policy innovations were just as or more important. All participant answers are presented in Annex 2.

1.4.3 WORKSHOP #1

The main aim of this first workshop was to **agree on a common destination** for FVC transformation, i.e., to define in broad terms what were the long-term objectives we wanted the food system to reach by 2050. To support this discussion, the VALUMICS team provided high-level **scientific evidence** demonstrating how the food system interacts with a number of planetary boundaries - climate change, nitrogen and phosphorous flows, land-system change, etc. (IPBES, 2019; IPCC, 2020; Rockström et al., 2009; etc.) - and what sustainable “biophysical scenarios” point towards (a reduction in animal food sources, etc.). The discussion also underlined key socio-economic challenges in the food system (employment, revenues, consumer prices, etc.) and analysed contrasting socio-economic trajectories for achieving France’s low carbon strategy for agriculture (based on an IDDRI report soon to be published), looking at the impacts both at the farm and at the industry level.

The break-out discussions focused on the key **long-term priorities** to address. To do so, three questions were raised:

1. Define the destination: where do we (the food system) need to get to?
2. Describe the locked-in situation (the systemic barriers to progress) and its key causes
3. Highlight which causes we need to tackle first and why

While there was a broad **consensus** on many of the objectives discussed, the conversation also brought out some **key dilemmas**, including:

- (i) the **risk of a dualization of the food system** and a potential split between different transition pathways as a result of **social inequalities**, with one the one hand, the emergence of sustainable food products only accessible to one segment of the population, and on the other hand, the prevalence of cheap and standardized food products/systems (the “low price” paradigm)
- (ii) the importance of reducing the food system’s carbon footprint while also preserving biodiversity, which raises potential **trade-offs** between different production practices/methods

- (iii) the necessity to provide **healthy and sustainable diets** at two levels: the level of the **plate composition** (increasing plant proteins/decreasing animal proteins) and the **product level** (reducing the impact of specific products). Processing industry representatives pointed out that the levers specific to these two aspects were different and that they had more power over the second lever, while consumers could drive a change in the product mix.
- (iv) The lack of a vision on the **role of technology** with regards to attaining sustainability targets and the need to better/collectively define “which kind of science and technology” should be prioritized for further development.

1.4.4 TOUCHPOINT

After looking at food system transformation from a general perspective during W#1, the touchpoint provided an opportunity to **deep dive into the specific issues that characterise individual FVCs** (dairy and protein crops) and unpack the main lock-ins preventing their transition. Overall, the group discussed the following obstacles:

1. **Competition/trade rules** leading to unsustainable forms of competitiveness
2. **Food environment** leading to unsustainable dietary patterns
3. **Lack of financing mechanisms** for sustainable agri-food initiatives
4. **Agricultural subsidies** failing to support sustainable practices
5. **Technological lock-ins** preventing shifting strategies

At the heart of the discussions lay the question of **markets**, the way in which they could either provide opportunities or obstacles to the development of sustainable FVCs, and whether they are in the reach of policy makers. With regards to **protein crops**: Stakeholders pointed out that although an expansion of the sector was possible and desirable (especially to reduce the protein deficit/dependency of Europe), it would depend on certain critical conditions. In a context of strong international competition in this sector, the need to manage the competitiveness of European producers and processors was particularly highlighted, especially for the feed industry. Two options were presented as a way forward: a technological solution and a market solution. On the technological side, the topic of NBTs - New Breeding Techniques - was discussed as a potential way to increase the yield stability of crops and therefore improve their profitability – although this is a controversial topic of public debate. Alternatively, developing segmented/high-value added supply chains based on European protein crops would require an increase in consumer willingness-to-pay for sustainably fed animal products or pulses.

Concerning the **dairy** FVC: one of the key discussions centred on the type of markets that the dairy sector should supply in the next years. The risk of having an export-oriented transition was raised since it has especially led to the production/development of industrial products such as powdered milk. Furthermore, the social perspectives of the sector were raised as a key challenge, in the context of a strong decline in the number of producers in the past decade which has oriented the FVC towards a more concentrated and specialised production. Aiming for a ‘quality turn’ in the sector’s strategy (a shift from a volume-based towards a value-based business model) was highlighted as a necessary way forward.

1.4.5 WORKSHOP #2

Once the general lock-ins were identified, the second Workshop aimed to have participants start to define **transition pathways** and investigate how FVC actors' strategy/business model could evolve in the short to medium-term to be on the right track. To do so, a "**back-casting approach**" was adopted (see figure below) whereby the 2050 vision discussed during the first workshop was used to develop concrete 2030 quantitative targets (e.g., how much wheat, dairy or protein crops would be consumed/produced by then). On this basis, participants discussed **what types of actions and strategic steps** needed to be taken to meet such targets in the short-term (throughout the next decade).

Four steps to design transition pathways

1. Set **2050 quantitative targets** for an EU sustainable food system: consumption and production levels – then translated into **2030 “intermediary” targets**
2. Specify what each **actors’ strategy / business model** looks like in 2030 at each stage: for farmers, processors, retailers, consumers – why are they **sustainable & fairer**?
3. Make explicit what **actions** they have taken from now to 2030 to get there: innovation, supply strategies, human resources, market repositioning / segmentation...
4. Identify the most critical changes needed in the **policy framework**: what and how?

Figure 5: Back-casting approach

To engage in such an exercise, it was first necessary to **find common ground on the definition of long-term 2030 objectives** as a landing point for FVC transformation. The objective here was not to build a strict consensus, but to agree on the general direction of travel, while recognizing potential disagreements and convergences on the scale of change needed/feasible in the next 10 years.

Then, participants reflected on what would be the **dominant strategies** at the production/processing/retail/consumer level by 2030. For example, in the wheat sector, it was pointed out that all companies and farmers needed to join forces to foster **innovations** which would play a key role. It was highlighted that some of the big feed companies are already starting to partner with food/retail companies to innovate on many aspects, and that we would be seeing many more synergies of the sort in the future. Increasing **trust and transparency** would also allow to foster consumer changes. On the other hand, an important obstacle for farmers/processors is **stranded assets**, as they have already invested a lot: this was pointed out as one aspect where the enabling environment should help them restructure their production site. Overall,

the transformation of the wheat FVC as a consequence of a decline in animal productions was considered feasible but strongly dependent on (i) **innovations** and (ii) **markets**.

1.4.6 WORKSHOP #3

The final half-day workshop aimed to **refine and improve the robustness** of the FVC transition pathways by **prioritising key actions**. Indeed, during the previous workshops, many levers had been put forth to promote a shift in the European food system, however, the objective here was to highlight the most important conditions for change (both quick wins and hard wins through a step-by-step process) and to specify what role each FVC actor should play.

Figure 6: A strategic trajectory, from quick to hard wins

For example, in the **dairy sector**, the three most important conditions discussed were:

- Producers align on environmental and animal welfare regulation: more sustainable policy framework, retailer role to inform the consumer on the dairy product they are selling
- Consumers shift to quality and be able to address extra price: information for all products included in processed dairy products, accompanied by state action – guidelines and procurement
- Fairness in the chain: distribution of the value between all business, tackle the imbalance in power, transparency

In the **protein crop FVC**, they were more oriented towards:

- New varieties and breeding techniques: no quick fix (need money/ investments but also a clear regulatory framework on NBTs); important role of public research institutions)

- Setting global sustainability standards to level the playing field: through sustainability assessment criteria to remove the gap between countries
- Consumption changes through public procurement: voluntary initiatives by local governments can be bold; but need to be backed by quantitative framework at the European level to bring to scale.

1.4.7 OUTCOME GATHERING

To bring the WS to a close, the final meeting was focused on discussing the draft of the Outcome Document. The aim was to foster:

- **Understanding** of and improvement to draft Outcome Paper
- **Collective and individual buy-in to key messages**, strategic direction and specific FVC transition pathways
- Collective and individual **active ownership** of the Outcome Paper

Several stakeholders were designated ahead of time to prepare and share remarks with the rest of the group about what they found compelling/missing in the paper.

The last meeting was also marked by a **call for collective action**. Participants were invited, in small groups of three, to reflect upon two questions: “what priority actions will you advocate for in your role as a key (economic) actor?” and “what priority actions are imperative from other key actors?”. This brought the VALUMICS Workshop Series to an end on a positive note by motivating participants to reflect on how they could contribute, at their level, to the transformation of FVCs.

1.5 STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS OF THE WS

1.5.1 STRENGTHS

One of the primary accomplishments of the VALUMICS Workshop Series was to succeed in creating **a conducive dialogue space**. Indeed, the workshops provided an original platform for stakeholders from a variety of different horizons to meet and discuss in a pre-competitive/pre-political format. One stakeholder from the European Commission saluted the fact that it “provide(d) a relatively neutral space” for discussion. Participants were generally enthusiastic about the fact that the whole process offered an occasion to “step out of the everyday business” and collectively discuss the challenges at hand to start building the future of the European food system. In fact, it was clearly acknowledged that there was a need to gather as a community and collaborate on such challenges. As a final statement, one participant commented:

*“There are – most of the time – no simple solutions to complex challenges. And the selected topic was for sure complex, involving many experts from different stakeholder communities. For sure, **collaboration will be key** to successfully tackle the challenge. So the overall – and in this way outstanding – conclusion for me: most experts followed the whole series of workshops, even though it was time consuming and demanding. My conclusion: **many people feel the need for change** – even if they do not have a simple solution.”*

The engaging and productive nature of the exchanges were particularly driven by the **diversity** of profiles around the (virtual) table: participants commented that “the diversity of actors makes it possible to take valuable input” and that “dialogues (are) always useful to understand the thinking/ideas of other stakeholders”. Nonetheless, because the WS brought together stakeholders from very different horizons across all levels of the European food system, part of the challenge was also to harmonise the collective thinking and obtain an agreement across the group on the general direction of travel. Deep diving into the specificity of each sector was crucial to steer away from superficial/vague statements and stakeholders’ tendency not to engage fully (nodding their heads in agreement while maintaining divergent opinions). Rather, framing the discussion around the protein transition was a provocative and uncompromising way of encouraging participants to address key points of tension (e.g., how to discuss a reduction in volumes consumed/produced in certain supply chains).

Workshop evaluation (3/3)

006

How do you rate the workshop series overall?

Figure 7: Final slido assessment

1.5.2 LIMITATIONS

The principal shortcoming that transpired throughout these workshop discussions was the **roadblock encountered in trying to get participants to discuss what they could do/commit to at the level of their own organizations/businesses** in order to contribute to the sustainable transformation of FVCs. On several occasions during break-out sessions, stakeholders were asked about what strategic shifts could be implemented at their level (e.g., “In terms of your organization/institution’s business model – what are you taking out of this dialogue in terms of commitment for European FVC progress?”). In response, participants often (though not always) deflected the question and pointed out solutions/changes that lay beyond the scope of their own activity.

For example, when one representative from retail was pressed to indicate how they could work towards eliminating unsustainable products from their shelves (i.e., retail choice editing), they indicated that this could not be their responsibility:

*“Yeah but who is doing that? Is it the retailer? *laugh* Or are we doing this because the law says we are not allowed to sell the products? Then it’s easy for us because we say then « it’s not our fault, it’s the politicians’ fault we are not allowed to sell this product ». Only putting the retailer in charge to clean the shelf, this won’t work.”*

In another instance, when a representative from the processing industry was questioned about how they could support the development of the protein crops production/sector, their response swung towards the need to develop research in new breeding techniques (NBTs) and to create a conducive legal framework in this domain. Workshop participants therefore had a tendency to “**pass the buck**” and assign responsibility to other FVC actors, most notably to consumers and policymakers who exert *outside pressure* onto FVCs. *Internal* shifts were not often considered. Thus, the transition pathways discussed by participants lacked an in-depth identification/consideration of the type of economic and structural reorganizations (especially in terms of business models/strategies) that could occur within FVCs in the next few years leading up to 2030.

2 MAIN LOCK-INS

As previously mentioned, a central step in the development of FVC transition pathways is the identification of the main obstacles – or “*lock-ins*” - preventing the shift to more sustainable FVCs. From a conceptual perspective, the notion of a “lock-in” refers to a situation in which several factors occur in combined interaction and create persistent path-dependencies, making it impossible to change the dominant trajectory of the system. This concept is borrowed from the literature on sociotechnical transitions and has been explored in a variety of different sectors. For example, Unruh (2000) has examined how technological and institutional co-evolutions have locked modern economies into fossil fuel-based energy systems and thus prevent the diffusion of carbon-saving technologies (a phenomenon labelled the “carbon lock-in”).

Closer to our own concerns with the protein transition, Magrini et al. (2018) and Meynard et al. (2013) have analysed the strong lock-in of the agri-food sector around a small number of dominant species, which hinders the emergence of diversified crops, and notably protein crops/plant-based products. Escaping such a “locked-in” situation often necessitates *co-evolutions/synchronised* changes in several parts of the system such as in political, social, economic and technical areas (Elzen et al., 2011). More specifically, Geels & Schot (2007) point to the necessity of combined pressures coming from the external socio-political environment (i.e. the “socio-technical landscape”) and from niche-innovations. In the case of the protein crop sector, Meynard et al. (2017) thus call for designing “coupled innovations” both upstream and downstream of FVCs in order to sustainably transform agrifood systems.

Building on the outcomes of the Workshop Series discussions, the following section presents in detail the critical socio-political “lock-ins” identified by participants across the three FVCs investigated (protein crops, wheat, dairy). It highlights the ways in which these lock-ins currently represent a critical challenge to the transformation of the food system and provides suggestions as to how the European policy framework might evolve.

1. CONSUMER HABITS

The challenge

Consumer change was overwhelmingly presented by WS stakeholders as a necessary *condition* to drive the transformation of European food value chains: “consumers need to become the real drivers, but this requires more transparency and willingness for informed food choices.” In particular, economic actors (retailers, processors) and policymakers pointed out that their hands were tied as long as consumer demand did not evolve towards sustainable choices. For example, one actor pointed out that industry-led initiatives could fail if consumers did not pick up on a new offer:

“You need a consumer driven process at some point, but this is very difficult, it requires a good timing. For example, we started organic brands in Austria: it was a niche, and it was a success, but other attempts on sustainability failed. Sometimes we were too early,

for example with the plastic-free bottle on one of our products, we had to stop. The question of synchronization with what the consumer wants is crucial...”

Another stakeholder discussed the critical limitations rooted in price considerations:

“The “low price” paradigm has a big influence in our food systems, which hinders the opportunity to bring alternatives and actual choices to consumers. (...) If innovative products from a sustainability perspective are not aligned with an expected price, it will be difficult to sell such products. In that case, it is hard to convince retailers to take up more sustainable products at a low cost.”

Although most actors thus placed a significant responsibility on consumers for ultimately driving the transition, they often lacked introspection and did not discuss how they could themselves play a role in guiding sustainable consumer choices through FVC businesses’ strategies or at the level of European policymaking (this was much more a topic of discussion at the local/municipal level).

To put things into context, policies in Europe have done little to target consumers’ eating habits. In fact, to date, Europe has not devised a comprehensive food policy. Only a few piecemeal strategies have been adopted, but they fail to address all food-related (health and environmental) issues in an integrated and coherent manner as most policies are focused on the prevention of overweight and obesity, such as the EU Action Plan on Childhood Obesity 2014-2020 or the 2007 Strategy for Europe on Nutrition, Overweight and Obesity-related health issues (IPES-Food, 2019). Furthermore, although some policy measures have been implemented at the national level by European Member States, a large majority of them have been relatively ineffective “soft” policy interventions such as informational and educational actions (Capacci et al., 2012 - see table below)

Table 1 Distribution of interventions by type of policy action.

Policy classification	Total no.	No. in Europe
<i>Interventions supporting more informed choice</i>	86	82
Advertising controls	6	5
Controls on advertising to children	5	4
Controls on general advertising	1	1
Public information campaigns	39	38
Nutrition education	35	35
For children at school	31	31
For adults/general public (e.g., at workplace)	4	4
Nutrition labeling	5	4
Nutrition information on menus	1	0
<i>Interventions changing the market environment</i>	43	39
Fiscal measures	4	3
Tax/subsidies on foods to the population at large	1	1
Subsidies to disadvantaged consumers	3	2
Regulation of meals	15	14
School meals (including vending-machine bans and provision of free fruit and vegetables)	13	13
Workplace cafeteria meals	2	1
Nutrition-related standards	1	1
Government action to encourage private-sector action	10	9
Measures to increase availability to disadvantaged consumers	2	2
Liability laws	1	0
<i>Interventions not explicitly targeted at healthy eating</i>	4	4
<i>Generic interventions</i>	6	6
Total	129	121

Table 2: European food policy interventions (Capacci et al., 2012)

The reluctance to implement “hard” market-based actions and adopt a more interventionist approach has frequently been attributed to the neo-liberal logic prevalent in current political thought which aims to preserve consumer sovereignty above all (Lang & Barling, 2013). However, Boubal (2019) has offered an additional explanation in the case of the French policy process on nutrition (not necessarily applicable to other European countries): she has pointed to the fact that it is often also an expression of the interest of private actors to mobilise resources towards nutrition communications/education campaigns as it is a way to avoid more constraining measures being placed onto them (e.g., requirements of product reformulation).

Designing a policy framework to guide consumer change

In spite of the general reluctance to include consumers’ plate in the scope of public policy, politicians have recently increasingly recognised that consumers’ eating behaviour is, to a large extent, conditioned by their “food environment” – including in the recent F2F strategy. According to the High-Level Panel of Experts on Food Security and Nutrition (HLPE), the “**food environment**” as “the physical, economic, political and socio-cultural context in which consumers engage with the food system to make their decisions about acquiring, preparing and consuming food.” (HLPE, 2017). The food environment approach has therefore increasingly recognised the role of FVC actors and policies in moulding consumers’ choices (Park & Barker, 2020; Vonthron et al., 2020). Below are a few proposals put forth during the Workshops Series that could be mobilised or reinforced in the next 10 years to help redirect consumer demand:

Environmental labelling: The question of environmental labelling has constituted a particular hotspot of food policy for a number of years. Although this instrument is typically considered a “soft” informational measure directed towards consumers, Dubuisson-Quellier (2016) has shown that it may also exert pressure onto supply-side companies to improve the environmental sustainability and composition of their products. Therefore, it also serves as a harder form of market intervention. At present, the European Union is reluctant to make this a mandatory measure, however it plans to examine ways to create a framework to harmonise voluntary initiatives (European Commission, 2020b). Some actors have indeed already started to come out with privately developed schemes: most recently, in France, a number of food and digital companies, including the app Yuka (which is now used by over 20 million people), have just launched the “Eco-score”. Much like the Nutri-score, it displays a colour coded assessment of the environmental impact of the product. The French government plans on developing its own public version by 2023.

(Voluntary) retail choice editing: Traditionally, retailers have been considered as passive “choice providers”, simply acting as a middleman between the food industry and food buyers (Gunn & Mont, 2014). Their sole role in this respect is to deliver a wide range of options to consumers to choose from. However, more proactive interventions have recently been implemented by retailers to reorient consumer choices towards sustainable products, including nudges. An “extreme” form of intervention is “choice editing” which refers to the elimination of unsustainable options with retail stores while mainstreaming sustainable products as default options (see VALUMICS Deliverable 6.4 for examples of choice editing strategies).

Figure 8: A retailer's perspective on choice editing

Public procurement: Finally, public procurement was often cited as a market-based tool easily available to public authorities to reorient consumer practices. Voluntary initiatives at the local/municipal level were pointed out as effective strategies to make bold changes: for example, the City of Ghent plans to introduce 50% of plant proteins in school meals. However, the necessity to build legislation and define guidelines at the European level was pointed out as a crucial step to bring local initiatives to scale. Furthermore, the current competition rules banning the procurement of local products was highlighted as a particular obstacle which needs to be addressed at the European level (although in practice, local government procurement officials have found ways around these rules by creative use of procurement criteria (Smith et al., 2016).

2. MARKET ORGANISATION: COMPETITION AND TRADE RULES

The challenge

Another key lock-in which was highlighted was the need for changes in the market (“there needs to be somewhere high market pressure, but it’s complicated and the signal needs to be sufficiently important”). Today, European FVC actors operate in a context characterised by strong competition, both on the internal EU market and internationally. Getting to a sufficient level of price- competitiveness is thus absolutely required for them to thrive. The competitive pressure has forced FVC operators to adopt a volume-oriented strategy based on economies of scale and the massification and concentration of production so as to cut production costs. This prevalent logic has been detrimental both from an environmental and a social perspective, as it is at the root of the intensification/industrialization/ specialisation of farming systems.

This “race to the bottom” constitutes a particularly strong “lock-in” across the three FVCs examined. For instance, strong international competition was pointed out as the main factor hindering the take-off of the protein crop sector in Europe as domestic production suffers from a significant lack of cost competitiveness compared to North and South American crops (Schreuder & Visser, 2014). As a result, despite the political appeal towards a greater European protein autonomy, the EU still has a significant protein deficit – notably for feed - and imports 70% of its needs. One way forward that has been proposed would be to implement a temporary period of market protection through non-tariff barriers to allow FVC actors to achieve economies of scale and reach a competitive advantage within Europe (Schiavo & Aubert, 2020).

In addition, the market structure exerts strong pressure on dairy and wheat FVCs to keep the cost of production low and therefore prevents a turn to more sustainable production. Given the strong level of competition between processors in the commodity wheat sector, there are important risks that supply strategies would shift from the EU to imports from the Black Sea countries if the cost of raw materials increases due to a shift to more sustainable farming practices.

Designing a favourable market organisation

To enable EU actors to raise their level of sustainability and fairness without being at risk of losing their market shares, it was deemed necessary to create a level playing field based on environmental standards. This holds true not only at the international level, but also in the Single Market.

A number of different policy options were put forth that could help redesign market incentives towards sustainable strategies.

A significant way forward to adapt market rules would be to modify the EU legislation to allow for **horizontal (or vertical) forms of cooperation between actors within FVCs** for sustainability purposes. Such arrangements may create opportunities for industry-wide initiatives to introduce better environmental and social practices at a collective level (and therefore avoid first-mover disadvantages). Such attempts have already been made in the past but were blocked by competition authorities: for example, in the Netherlands, a group of chicken farmers, broiler meat processors and retailers could not pursue their initiative to replace conventional chicken with products

under higher animal welfare norms (ACM, 2015). In the UK, the application of competition law prevents companies from agreeing on price levels to their suppliers that would ensure decent wages throughout their supply chains (Farquahr, 2011). In view of aligning competition rules/policy with the Green Deal objectives, the European Commission recently has launched a formal discussion and call for submissions on this question (European Commission, 2020a) and more specifically on the definition of “sustainability agreements” (Batchelor et al., 2020). Such agreements would indeed clarify the contours of legal types of coordination between competitors. This question is notably being raised in the context of the revision of the ‘Guidelines on Horizontal Cooperation Agreements’ and could therefore have a significant impact in the long run.

Furthermore, another market-driven option to foster the transition towards sustainable FVCs would be to **internalize environmental and social costs** into the cost of food products sold/traded on the market (Bellmann et al., 2019). The price-correcting measure would make sustainable products/productions more competitive than their conventional counterparts and would push downstream FVC actors (processors/retailers/consumers) to shift their supply strategies towards sustainable products. Although this approach may be highly effective in theory, it poses significant political and methodological challenges:

- i) At a political level, such a market-correcting measure could not be applied solely at a national level and/or without the introduction of tariff barriers, otherwise the risk would be that processors turn to imports for cheap raw material. It would therefore require strong international coordination. Furthermore, the question then becomes: who should pay for the extra cost of unsustainable products—public funds or consumers? If consumers were to bear this additional financial burden, this would in turn raise the question of putting in place additional social nets such as food stamps or a food social security (Coulet, 2020).
- ii) From a methodological perspective, the calculation of external social and environmental costs is also highly challenging. Nonetheless, such an exercise has already been conducted, for example in Germany by Pieper et al. (2020) or by the True Cost Accounting initiative (Soil & More Impacts, 2020) to integrate the climate costs of food products.

Finally, the promotion of sustainable productions/FVCs could be embedded into trade agreements and/or non-tariff barriers through **PPM-based restrictions** (Charnovitz, 2002; Gaines, 2002). Indeed, Processes and Production Methods have been put forth as a legal instrument to design potentially discriminatory trade measures against unsustainable products as it would allow sustainable products to not suffer from competitive disadvantage. However, given the international context in particular with respect to trade, it is unlikely that such changes could be approved in the near future through a multilateral process.

3. AGRICULTURAL SUBSIDIES

How do CAP subsidies support unsustainable strategies?

Over the past 40-50 years, the CAP has been widely acknowledged as a major driver of agricultural intensification (Assandri & et al., 2019). From its very inception in 1962, the CAP's main objective was to ensure Europe's self-sufficiency in food and therefore increase agricultural productivity and modernize the sector (Berthelot et al., 2013). In so doing, the CAP has effectively contributed to an increase in farm sizes and the specialization of production. Furthermore, the CAP indirectly supports the industrial livestock sector: a report released by Greenpeace in 2019 revealed that a staggering 28.5-32.6 billion euros went into the livestock sector (either directly to livestock farms or farms producing fodder) – effectively representing between 18-20% of the EU's total annual budget (Greenpeace, 2019). This has had dramatic consequences on the diversity of landscapes and on-farm biodiversity (Huyghe et al., 2014).

Designing a conducive policy framework

Although the proposed CAP reform generally boasts the same objectives and pillar structure as before, the main change it introduces is an increased subsidiarity for Member States and a higher flexibility in their use of financial allocations. The stated goal is to simplify and modernize the process and deliver higher performance according to each country's specific circumstances. Following nine common objectives, each State will therefore have to produce a Strategic Plan which defines specific national targets. Although the reform claims to increase environmental and climate ambition by dedicating 40% of the total CAP budget to climate action, NGOs have criticized this claim based on the actual examination of the legislative proposal (BirdLife, 2018; European Environmental Bureau, 2018; Greenpeace, 2019).

One of the main tools introduced to support sustainable practices is the creation of “**eco-schemes**”. Member states will have to dedicate a part of the direct payments budget (Pillar 1) to farmers engaged in environmental practices which go beyond existing eco-conditionality practices. However, no minimum budget is defined for this. Therefore, NGOs have warned that the risk is that in theory, Member States could allocate a symbolic 1 euro. Another risk is that normal direct payments could count as eco-schemes because they are distributed under eco- conditionality (BirdLife, 2018). Overall, given that Member States will be able to fully decide the content of these eco-schemes (European Commission, 2019b), there is no guarantee these will contribute to preserving grasslands.

The extent to which current negotiations will or will not enable change is quite uncertain. On top of that, all tools that used to support specific FVCs in a targeted manner (i.e. coupled subsidies and quotas) have (almost) been removed in recent decades to align the CAP with competition and trade rules. This begs the question of whether the CAP may be useful in supporting a protein transition and reaching the underlying FVC-specific quantitative targets.

3 FVC TRANSITION PATHWAYS

The following section highlights the preliminary transition pathways developed for the wheat, protein crops and dairy value chains during the course of the VALUMICS Workshop Series. Because they result from a stakeholder-based process, they do not attempt to capture all of the dimensions involved in FVC transitions, but rather focus on envisioning the **specific role played by each FVC actor** in bringing European Food Value Chains towards a more sustainable and fair system.⁵

1. THE WHEAT FOOD VALUE CHAIN

Bold vision: By 2030, Europe will have increased the environmental quality of the wheat produced, enabling in turn to increase the value added by tons of wheat produced throughout EU food value chains. This “quality turn” is accompanied by a slight decrease in the total quantity produced linked to both a decrease in the total feed demand (itself resulting from a drop in total meat demand) and the increase in protein crops in arable rotations. Those changes are driven on the one hand, by consumers whose consumption practices evolve towards less animal products and healthier food products. Policy changes also play a key role by offering support to farmers to accomplish the transition, fostering the development and uptake of innovations and setting harmonized trade rules with competing countries on the global wheat market.

What are the key steps taken by actors to foster the transition of FVCs?

Besides changes in quantity, the quality of the wheat produced improves, based on agroecological and organic practices. **Farmers** develop strategies and new cropping techniques to face climate change, thanks also to the availability of new cultivars and the work done by **breeders** to develop those.

Processors become closer to consumers through communication, but also because some value chains have become shorter to accommodate the wish of **consumers** to reconnect their consumption to producers.

Feed producers develop ways to shed light on the importance of providing quality feed meal to farmed animals (including for aquaculture) for the quality of final food products. Technological innovations have enabled them to reduce production costs while handling a greater variety of raw material / feedstuff.

“**Traditional**” or “**local**” **bakers** remain important bread producers, supported by an increasing number of consumers. This provides high value outlets for flour millers which in turn aids economic stability in the wheat value chain.

However, a number of key questions remain open: What quality of flour and wheat will **secondary processors** be using, with which consequences or constraints for farmers? Will they be able to value organic or agroecological wheat in processed products? This will have to do with what retailers will be wanting to put on shelves, and

⁵ As said in the introduction, transition pathways for the tomato and salmon value chains will be subject of other project publications, as they were not covered in this workshop series.

how retailers-processors relationship evolve. On another note, is the demand from the starch industry or the biofuel industry likely to increase.

2. THE PROTEIN CROP FOOD VALUE CHAIN

Bold vision: By 2030, Europe will have at least doubled its production and consumption of plant protein. Producers will increasingly integrate protein crops in arable rotations/cover crops/pastures, while the agroindustry will have invested in a number of processing units to enable the collection and processing of more diverse crops at a regional scale. Finally, consumers will favour a more balanced protein intake between animal and plant protein, partly fostered by downstream innovation in plant-based products.

What are the key steps taken by actors to foster a transition of FVCs?

While for some supply chains, the main challenge is to decrease and/or reorient consumption and production towards more sustainable practices, the legume supply chain currently represents a niche sector and must therefore, first and foremost, be structured. To do this:

A majority of **producers** (including conventional ones) begin to implement strategies of crop diversification and integrate legumes into longer rotations as well as in adapted feeding systems. This is made possible through the work done by **breeders** (especially supported by public research institutions) to develop new varieties/breeding techniques for protein crops which provide better resistance & higher yields - therefore making them more profitable and appealing to farmers.

Upstream processors also play an important part by making tangible investments in the necessary equipment/infrastructure and logistics to set up regional collecting/storage and manufacturing units in order to valorise more diversified productions.

At the **downstream processing** level, innovations in plant-based products and the integration of plant protein as a mainstream ingredient in processed foods helps create market outlets for protein crops. All major food companies (including ones originally specialised in animal products) create several lines of plant-based products. A higher acceptance by **consumers** of plant-based options is fostered by the increasing presence of whole and processed plant-based protein in their food environment.

In parallel, **feed processors** also invest in the necessary R&D and technologies to improve the nutritional quality, digestibility and protein content of protein crops (beyond soy) for feed in order to better integrate them into current feedstuff produced.

3. THE DAIRY FOOD VALUE CHAIN

Bold vision: By 2030, the dairy value chain succeeds to evolve toward more sustainable production by going against two main trends followed by the dairy sector since the milk quotas were abolished in 2015. To tackle environmental and health issues, milk production is successfully reduced reversing the continuous milk production increase of the previous years. At the same time, dairy farmers follow new production strategies, with more extensive management of the soil and of the animals in small farm structures. Thus, the steady decline in the number of dairy farms in the EU based on production intensification and concentrations is stopped, despite the reduction in livestock numbers.

What are the key steps taken by actors to foster the transition of FVCs?

The dairy value chain in 2030 evolves toward more sustainable production practices, in line with a sustained consumer demand for environmentally friendly products.

Dairy farmers start to follow higher value-added production strategies, with more extensive management of the soil and of the animals. Farmer's wellbeing increases following better rewards for quality products and environmental protection. Producers rely on the development of technologies and new farming skills to manage the transition. At the same time special support mechanisms are set to help existing farms that previously invested into unsustainable production techniques.

Farmers get involved in referencing dynamics with **local operators** in order to guarantee the consumption of locally produced milk and dairy products. The setting up of local production, collection and processing networks is therefore a key issue. **Retailers** help in that respect by providing specific contracts with extra payment to farmers taking specific environmental commitments. Milk becomes better traced and valued in longer food processing chains that use milk as an ingredient – though not “apparent” for consumers.

Finally, the level of production decreases but given the reduction of domestic consumption, the EU remains a net exporter in the dairy sector.

CONCLUSION

This report has sought to help bridge the gap between the ambitious biophysical targets laid out in several 2050 EU food system scenarios and food value chain transformations. The results from the VALUMICS multi-stakeholder workshops were drawn upon in order to begin developing several transition pathways that highlight mechanisms to facilitate the transformation of FVCs to reach 2030 targets in the medium term. Key to this process is emphasizing the existing socio-political lock-ins that currently prevent environmental transformations across European FVCs. Three lock ins were elaborated upon in this report: 1) consumer habits, 2) market organisation (competition and trade rules) and 3) the current agricultural policy framework.

In order to confront intransigent food consumption habits, several levers for change were proposed to reshape the food environment including through environmental labelling, retail choice editing and public procurement. With respect to market organization, a number of policy mechanisms were put forth that would seek to level the playing field between sustainable and conventional producers, including PPM-based restrictions and “sustainability agreements”. To overcome the challenges posed by current agricultural subsidies, eco-schemes should play a central role in conditioning direct payments around environmental criteria, but the current reform proposal is insufficient to meet this objective.

In order for Europe to meet its ambitious climate and biodiversity targets, while addressing fairness within food value chains, ambitious transformations will need to be made by actors at all level of the FVC, from farmers to processors to retailers and consumers. Preliminary transition pathways were co-designed with WS stakeholders that identified the specific role that each actor will play to drive the multi-level transformation of FVCs by 2030. This multi-stakeholder response points towards the utility of engaging in collaborative dialogues such as those organized through the VALUMICS Workshop Series. Future research and policy responses should draw upon these results, and continue emphasizing the complex interactions between actors across the EU food system.

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ANNEXES

ANNEX 1: CONCEPT NOTE

CONCEPT NOTE

VALUMICS WORKSHOPS SERIES

Recent high-level publications have explored what a sustainable European food system could look like by 2050. They all point towards three main elements: the need for dietary change, towards an increase in vegetal consumption and a decrease in animal protein sources; the requirement to reduce food waste and losses by at least 50%; and the necessity to redesign farming systems, by relying on a much greater diversity and an absolute decrease in the use of inputs. While such imperatives are clearly highlighted in the recent Farm2Fork strategy published by the European Commission as part of the Green Deal, their potential implications for food value chains organisation & governance have remained largely unexplored. Yet, food businesses (collectors, processors, retailers) are today key in shaping our food system and play an important social and economic role at the EU level.

Against this backdrop, the European research project VALUMICS seeks to characterise and develop food value chain transition pathways towards a sustainable, fair and resilient food system by 2050. In other words, it aims to identify the concrete policy and economic levers which will steer the transformation of European supply chains in the next 10 years. However, in this perspective, contrasting visions and underlying dilemmas have emerged over how supply chain actors and sectors should adapt to the pressing sustainability imperative, especially in the wake of the COVID-19 crisis. While some promote a market-led transition driven by internationalised value chains and specialised production systems, others defend the need to reterritorialize and diversify food systems notably through the development of a more local industry base. As a result, the debate often becomes a dialogue of the deaf and falls short of expectations to propose and move forward towards concrete solutions.

The issue of a 'protein transition' provides a revealing illustration of this bottleneck. Indeed, while the need to reduce animal protein consumption within the EU is widely acknowledged, the extent to which this should translate into a reduction in animal protein production is no settled matter. For certain stakeholders, EU natural advantages and high levels of carbon efficiency in pork or poultry systems provide a justification for increasing production and exporting it towards third countries with a skyrocketing demand. Others contend on the contrary that European livestock production should follow dietary changes and significantly reduce over the next 10-20 years, giving way to more sustainable plant-based and alternative protein productions (which in turn raises another debate about the most fitting alternatives). However, in the current COVID-19 context characterised by a strong necessity to maintain jobs, the economic prospects provided by the livestock sector - which currently employs a third of agroindustry workers (that is, 1.2 million jobs) - are not easily tossed aside.

Acknowledging underlying tensions and exploring in an open-minded way different approaches is thus essential to move beyond a sterile confrontation between two worldviews and start identifying critical solutions in a productive discussion around the main obstacles and levers towards the transformation of European value chains.

CONCEPT NOTE

WORKSHOP SERIES OBJECTIVES:

Bringing together diverse perspectives from policy making, business, civil society and thought leaders (science and think tanks), the W8 Workshop Series will define transition pathways for food value chain transformation, making clear both economic and policy implications. The objective will be to collectively identify and discuss specific lock-ins and leverage points likely to bring about more sustainable supply chains. To achieve this, the workshops will:

1. Build trust and common understanding of key scenarios
2. Explore and unpack prioritised lock-ins to achieving desired change
3. Focus on major leverage points and their applicability – geographical and sectoral
4. Build up transition pathways and related narratives

In blending an improbable network of twenty participants, we will recognise both divergence and alignment. Building trust and common understanding will be key to delivering a compelling outcome paper co-created and co-owned by all to present the main policy challenges collectively identified.

CALENDAR AND WORKSHOP SERIES KEY COMPONENTS:

October-mid-November	Workshop participants start engaging in dialogue through a collaborative iterative written exercise, initiated through a virtual Kick Off gathering . Two round of iterative exchange will inform the W8 Workshop Series agenda
Friday 6 November, 15:00-16:30 CET	
Tuesday 17 November, 15:00-18:00 CET	Workshop#1 virtual gathering: Series of active sessions considering key scenarios, a common destination and agreeing on weighted lock-ins
Tuesday 24 November, 15:00-16:30 CET	Touch point#1 3 x sub-groups meet for 1.5 hour for lock-in deep dives supported by lock-in briefing notes
Tuesday 1 December, 15:00-18:00 CET	Workshop#2 virtual gathering: Further develop policy asks and related policy impact pathways using the common narrative and vision. Longer working sessions interrupted by touch points for groups to share progress, request inputs and re-energize.
Tuesday 8 December, 15:00-16:30 CET	Touch point#2 3 x sub-groups meet for 1.5 hour for lever deep dives supported by lever (and trade-off) briefing notes
Monday 14 December, 15:00-18:00 CET	Workshop#3 virtual gathering: Value chain specific transition pathways developed, refined and adjusted. Narratives developed and commitments made to ensure collective progress.
Tuesday 12 January, 15:00-16:30 CET	Follow-up meeting to ensure co-creation process and collective validation of WP8 Workshop Series outcome document to be published at the end of January

ANNEX 2: COLLABORATIVE WRITTEN CONVERSATION

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COLLABORATIVE WRITTEN CONVERSATION COMPILATION

INTRODUCTION

The following is the compilation of the numerous responses to the four intentionally provocative questions we put to all participants to the Workshop Series. We have not edited the responses and have maintained anonymity. Each mini-paragraph represents a separate contribution. We have, nevertheless, highlighted what we consider to be some of the key words and phrases for easier navigation. This makes for a long, messy but gem-filled document that we feel has real value in and of itself. Please try and find the time to read through this, allow it to nourish the workshop conversations and feel able to make direct reference to it.

QUESTION 1: FOOD VALUE CHAINS FOR SUSTAINABLE FOOD SYSTEMS: WHAT IS AT STAKE?

Several food value chain actors contend that most challenges our food system faces can be tackled relying first and foremost on technological and scientific innovations. Would you agree with this view? If yes, why? If not, what alternatives do you see to transform food value chains so that they contribute to a more sustainable and fairer food system?

I tend to agree as I doubt that we can do any transformation without any contribution from a technology or scientific side. But for sure the question seems too general - we cannot make any generalisation to all value chains in the food sector.

Technological and scientific advances are certainly a necessary, even imperative, part of the response. The world population is growing. Aiming to wind our food systems back to what they delivered 50 years ago (or so) does not seem to appreciate the need, the complexities and the challenges at production, processing and consumption stages today. This may not be the only factor that needs adjustment, but without appropriate use of better know-how and technologies I fail to see how we will be able to provide a fair and sustainable (in the full sense of economics, social and environmental) response.

Yes, but not only technological innovations; we need diversity of different innovations (social, organizational, etc.). Besides, innovations, we need also change in policy and business strategies.

It is much more about governance and getting the prices right (internalize external costs) than about technology. Technology is a means to an end. Not an end in itself.

Technological and scientific innovations have a role to play. However, the application of such innovation is dependent upon both private investment and funding and state investment and direction. In addition, the policy and societal environments are important drivers of transition as they impact in turn upon decisions made by food value chain actors. The politics of how state intervention is determined is a key to driving and understanding opportunities for change. Crises and risks are important stimulants of political and policy action.

No, value chain sustainability does not rely only on technology and science. But on the best balance between environment, economic challenges vs market and consumer needs (raw material volumes, proteins rates, health, affordable prices).

Here are the questions that we need to think about to build more sustainability: What is the right level of price to be paid by consumers? How can we better balance value sharing along the chain? How can we better valorize the best farming practices? How can we drive the market towards a fairer competition between companies and brands (reducing lobbies and food standardization)?

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Tech. and scientific innovation are a key element, but there is room for a **change of business culture** (innovative business models and change of mentality), new ways of working with consumers and stakeholders, **trust and transparency** in the supply chain and incentives of various sorts (including financial incentives).

Science and technology can contribute to the overall solution, but **not alone** and by itself. Fairer food systems with food value chains suitable for wider sustainability need **inclusiveness and openness/transparency**. We need to assume that all food on the market is safe, healthy and with minimum acceptable quality. Policy, governance and **standards** must be uniformly applied, and **TRUST** established for achieving sustainable and fairer food system.

Innovative technology and science will contribute to solving challenges of our food systems, however **not in isolation**. The implementation of innovations to solve common problems of the food system need to consider multi-stakeholder involvement, inclusiveness (all stakeholders affected including civil society), and transparency of information regarding social, economic and environmental benefits and risks.

Don't agree, more **transparency** will help as well

Technological and scientific innovations will contribute for sure but **more as a tool than as a driver**. First and foremost will be **consumer demand and its perception by providers of food - retailers and food services** (and this is a driver that is not easy to influence or nudge, you can quickly get the opposite reactions to the ones expected); **policies** may also play a role but again they are not easy to design.

I do not agree with the view that "most challenges our food system faces can be tackled relying first and foremost on technological and scientific innovations". It is proven that to fit within planetary boundaries, our **food system must undergo significant changes**, including a decrease in animal-based production, an increase in vegetal protein sources, and a massive reduction of pesticide uses.

Technological innovations have certainly a role to play in transforming food systems. But the question is **what technology, and what innovation?** What are the principles we follow to deliver those innovations? **Social innovations are equally if not more important** (in industrial food systems) to move things forward. This includes **new ways to organise the value chains**, sharing tools, socialising risks... innovations include our understanding of ecosystems and how are we able to build synergies and maximise natural cycles. The key is **what principles do we follow to plan innovation** (e.g. the AE 13 principles).

QUESTION 2. PROMOTING HEALTHY AND SUSTAINABLE DIETS

To what extent should a reduction in animal protein consumption translate into a reduction in animal protein production within Europe? In other words, what should be the contribution of European producers to the provision of sustainable animal proteins to the rest of the world?

According to INCA17 surveys, we consume 45% excess protein for example, that is to say 90 grams per day and per person instead of the 52-gram recommendation, and 25% excess sugar. This overconsumption is the first thing to tackle: eating less is not depriving oneself, but eliminating excess. Afterres2050 proposes to **reduce our total protein overconsumption by 50%**; to reduce the proportion of sugar in our energy intake from 14% to 11% (the recommended value is 10%) Animal protein now represents 61% of our protein intake, that is to say around 1 million tons of animal protein for 640.000 tons of plant protein. **Yet animal protein production has far more impact than plant protein production**, as it takes between 2 and 10 kg of plant food to produce 1 kg of meat. France thus devotes 80% of its agricultural areas to animal feed: 35% of grasslands, 17% of forage crops, 15% of areas planted with cereals and

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oilseed crops intended for animal feed, the majority of exported cereals (as they are forage cereals for animal feed); without considering the co-products such as bran or beetroot pulp. Afterres2050 thus proposes to **reverse the respective proportions of animal and plant protein in our diet**, that is to say to cover our protein needs with about 60% of plant and 40% of animal origin.

In my view (as an environmental activist :) **animal protein consumption should be significantly decreased in Europe**. The level of consumption should be chosen as a medium level to minimize the impact of our food diets while maintaining a sufficient amount and quality of proteins.

In terms of climate protection, it **should decrease**. No percentage but real costs should be calculated (product prices are too low).

Yes, animal protein consumption should **decrease** in Europe. It is hard to say to what extent. Yet it cannot be totally excluded, and **all of the sources above** should be in a sustainable diet, but in **balanced** amounts.

Animal protein consumption in quantity and in share should **decrease**. A key driver for setting an aspirational target should be its **acceptability** for all persons affected, the **pathway** (sufficient time to adapt, **ownership and support**) seems more important than the goal itself, the setting of which cannot escape a certain degree of subjectivity (not easy to match with ownership). Similarly, deciding between types of animal proteins on the base of sustainability should integrate **all dimensions of sustainability, environmental and climatic**, but also **social and economic**. One evident example are ruminant-based products: bad in terms of climate, but with positive contribution to environmental dimensions, and even more on economic and social (not speaking of cultural with the rural and food heritage). Therefore, I don't think it's reasonable to propose any figure, just an **unquantified decrease**.

Alternative proteins, plant protein, fish to the extent it complies with **sustainable fishing** and aquaculture. For other types of meat, the start should be convincing the consumer to eat **less but high quality, sustainable meat** (as a specialty).

It should **decrease**. A good reference point is the planetary health diet, though culturally adapted. **It does not matter so much what type** of origin animal products have - though they should be **produced according to agroecological/organic/circular economy principles**.

Yes. But that's not a goal per se, is the consequence of a transition towards sustainable food systems. The **type of ASF is not important**, the key is to be able to transition towards **circular production systems (agroecology)** thus basing production more on **ecological leftovers** and much less on crop feeds.

Shifting subsidies away from factory farming is a Nr 1 priority. Once subsidies are redirected and market failures addressed **meat production will inevitably decrease, prices would go up, consumption down**. This should be accompanied by transition measures, including **social safety nets, VAT** etc. (policy packagings), to avoid the cost of the transition to be paid by the most vulnerable.

Protein consumption could be reconfigured for Europe - this would involve a **decrease in animal protein**. The type of protein produced should fit into sustainable forms of **mixed farming** (which reduce CO2 emissions) and fit the climate conditions and land quality and use for agricultural and horticultural production of the different regions of Europe, **without impacting adversely on land use outside of Europe** (notable through imported animal feed).

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Per capita consumption of animal protein **may need to decrease** to stay within sustainable planetary boundaries. Dairy should be reduced by abolishing subsidies to sustain current intensive farming practices. Same for beef from intensive farming based on imported feeds, **grass-fed and restorative practices for beef are fine if true cost of food is known and transparent to the consumer**. Fish consumption should be encouraged while staying within sustainable levels, taking note of **feed impacts** for aquaculture.

We base our view on research and scientific reports. For example, <https://eatforum.org/eat-lancet-commission/>. In general, the path pointed out is: **reducing animal proteins**. And if animal proteins are consumed, the better options are **fish and poultry**. Ruminants **must be avoided** in any case.

I am convinced that we will see a **reduced protein consumption** per capita over time. Not at least as we will see an increased focus on reducing the food waste in the future. But we will also be more aware on the amount of protein we are eating. On the prioritisation of animal protein types I believe that we will see a **more balanced consumption** and that means that we will **see more proteins coming from fish** as we here can do a **more sustainable production of high value animal protein** compared to the other sources.

The average meat consumption in Europe has most probably to be **reduced** and it is likely that existing trends we have seen in certain types of meat will continue. The current trends in Europe show that poultry consumption is increasing, beef going down and pig meat is more or less stable. One question is, to what extent we can and want to accelerate these trends. **It may be problematic and possibly counter-productive to try imposing a drastic change against cultural values or dietary habits**. Then there could be a risk that **the share of imported animal protein increases while the animal production in Europe goes down**. This would require reducing the need for animal protein imports in accordance with reduced animal protein production. Finally, another question is whether Europe has a role to play in global meat supplies, considering the fact that Europe is highly efficient in livestock production. **The basis for possible reduction of livestock production in certain regions in Europe could be linked to the respective emissions of farms when they cannot be mitigated through technical means and are a source of distortion**.

All types of animal protein should remain available, with a **preference to low-impact products** (wild fish, organic meats).

Meat production has been debated - not sure to what extent it should be decreased, but indeed the **farming systems should be prioritised based on environmental considerations**. **Seafood from aquaculture should be prioritised** since it is an effective farming system in terms of feed conversion ratio and can be efficiently operated in the ocean, thus not competing with land use. Moreover, it has a favourable nutrition content to support a sustainable diet. However, **development of alternative feed (e.g. insects, micro algae etc.) will need to be prioritised along with farming technologies**.

QUESTION 3: RECONFIGURATIONS OF PRODUCTION AND TRADE

In your view, should animal protein consumption decrease in Europe and, if so, to what extent? What type(s) of animal protein (beef, poultry, dairy, fish...) should be prioritised as part of a sustainable diet?

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Globalized agriculture including feed imports and meat exports do not close natural /nutrient cycles. A higher degree of self-sufficiency, more regional production, city region food systems provide alternative and better frameworks for then producing with low environmental and social standards for the world market.

Seen on global world level **animal protein production must be reduced**. Plus the chain between production and consumption must be as short as possible. If animal proteins are produced, they must be **consumed as local as possible**. In order to keep CO2 emissions as low as possible.

Export of animal proteins beyond Europe should **not be a priority**.

To a certain degree you should expect that we will see a **reduction** but here we have to take the **import/export balance** into consideration and as this balance hasn't been mentioned here it is difficult to foresee. I have a feeling that we in the future will see more local production and less transport of meat over long distances as this will contribute negatively to the sustainability profile for the proteins we are consuming. **What we can contribute with will most likely be technology and know-how on how to do an efficient local production.**

Same reduction as worldwide share

I don't yet have a sufficient understanding of the risks and opportunities related to this question for providing an educated answer. But I do think it is a **burning question!**

This is a **tricky question**. We need to strike the **right balance** between the animal production and the environmental goals.

In terms of global trade -import-export in Europe, this is a **complex scenario ! Self-sufficiency** in terms of production and consumption should be assessed for global geographic regions and global strategies discussed. The **economic viability** (profitability) of the industries are always the driving force (so **export is an economic incentive**), but national, regional and global strategies need to have a common or aligned strategies (not one solution for all in terms of production) - **this is a main challenge** and can be addressed through a common vision of solving global challenges, e.g. hunger, climate change etc.

Europe to position itself as a producer of high-quality, sustainably produced meat

Sorry for having anticipated this question already... Food systems are closely interlinked; they are not working in isolation. Although we hear now calls for **food sovereignty**, it does make sense to produce commodities according to where we reach the best resource efficiency and where there is a comparative advantage. Europe reaches good performances in cereal production and exports its surplus. Presumably, we should continue trading to deal with oversupply and deficit. Diversification is certainly desirable, but it needs to make sense from an agronomic point of view and from an economic point of view. It would seem appropriate to have a global vision of food production including its environmental impact. As explained before, considering efficiency in livestock production, there is merit for Europe to continue playing a certain role in supplying meat particularly if producers can show the example of producing animal protein in a sustainable manner that can eventually be reflected in **life cycle assessments**.

Provided market failures are addressed (including GHG externalities) and subsidies are phased out, sustainable trade could play a role in supporting the ASF sectors in Europe. At the same time is likely that if a real transition from landless systems to sustainable ASF production happens, export oriented ASF value chains will struggle to keep the pace with external markets.

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Competition should therefore be based on quality rather than quantity, which is also more consistent with EU position in the markets. Simultaneously EU markets should be protected from lower standards ASF products (i.e. Mercosur agreement). It is OK to have forms of protectionism if this is to protect producers and consumers.

It is difficult (if possible) to plan ex ante what would be the optimum contribution of the EU to sustainable world animal protein consumption. It seems that currently EU animal protein sectors are quite competitive and, in most sectors, contribute to answering the world consumption. This is true for high value added animal products (often also more sustainable - in the 3 dimensions - in their production process than their equivalent commodities), but also for certain commodities where the 'sustainability performance' of the EU seem intuitively better than in average in the rest of the world. The challenge is to find ways to internalise these sustainability dimensions into the market mechanisms, either through taxes (not easy, see resistances on carbon border tax, which btw only addresses one aspect of sustainability), though labelling or green alliances to align the different sustainability requirements in the world.

Carbon footprint of livestock protein needs to be considered and logistics involved in exporting protein foods from Europe. In this context, the feed used needs to be taken into account: is it coming from truly sustainable sources or imported? International trade is needed for some foods and should be assessed on basis of true cost of inputs, CO2 footprint vs. products produced. Certainly, no subsidies should be allowed for exported proteins that might disrupt local dependency on own capacity to produce. However, famine situations and interventions might need different considerations.

4. TRANSFORMING FOOD VALUE CHAINS

Who are the value chain actors that should drive the change, and what are the best strategies to do so?

State subsidies and inducements are a primary influence on agricultural production decisions at farm level, beyond the agri-geography of the farm's land. Secondly, market opportunities can be shaped by the State, and by the corporate retailers. Each protein sector has particular structural features, notably in the processing stages that need to be addressed. Large scale financial investment strategies can be a driver of change, also in a variety of ways.

First of all, a level playing field (market incentives, action against market concentration) is needed for all actors - then the big won't be so big in the future. Essentially, we need a closer collaboration in the region to establish regional value chains.

All actors could play a role. We need small companies to engage, because the employment, value creation, proximity, etc. they provide are central aspects of sustainability (not only environmental sustainability, but also social and economic sustainability). We need big companies to engage because they have the largest impact.

Actors having the necessary insight and willingness to try to change the state of the art. Most likely that will be a combination between supermarkets/retail, processors and feed producers.

Everyone. Many food producers in the EU are small and micro and they need to play a part (considering it may be more challenging for more traditional food SMEs than innovative food start-ups that already base their business model on offering a sustainable product).

Producers will implement technologies and shift towards more sustainable practices and the food industry and retail will have a key role in the transition by providing the consumers with healthy, sustainable choices.

VALUMICS WORKSHOPS SERIES

But this change needs to be **promoted and motivated by strategic goals and commitment** while respecting the cultural heritage of Europe and maintaining the biodiversity of the region - guided by **science-based assessments**, transparency of information and multi-stakeholder involvement at industry, sectoral, national and regional level and including civil society. Having said that not sure how to **combat the power of the global international corporations or somehow create a win-win situation?**

Big and medium players including retailers are the ones driving, analysing and addressing **consumer behaviour**. This includes cooperatives and POs that should be the level for farmers to be on equal footing. **Small and micro enterprises**, farmers are important though to host **innovations and emerging trends** on the one hand and to keep alive the (direct) contact between agriculture and consumers with its high benefits in terms of economic and social benefits. **Strategies should be dual and balanced : level playing field (at world / EU level)**, codes of conducts/due diligence, labelling, certification for an enhanced competition integrating sustainability concerns for the big; sufficient space for local food systems (not protectionism, local markets, not made in a certain country) and short food supply chains through green public procurement, support to all farmers markets, quality labels, education programmes etc..

1) Consumer needs to raise awareness on environmental impacts of agriculture **2) CAP** needs to valorize GAP and penalize too intensive ways of production **3) Competition rules on market** need to be adjusted to allow **less concentration** and **more space for small players** with better practices and shorter chains.

All the actors in the value chain need to play a role in driving the change. **Producers** and farmers (adopting new processes and implementing new products); **researchers** (providing evidence), **retailers and processors** (way they buy things, way they steer their customers: corporate responsibility) and governments (changing behaviour). **Governments** should develop their own sustainable food strategies. A **food council** in which all the chain actors are represented is the perfect vehicle to make a good strategy and to make sure all actors are involved and help playing their role in the implementation / realization of the food strategy.

All of them. Retail has an important role to play, considering their position in the value chains. They can impose stricter rules to suppliers to protect consumers, they can ensure **transparency and traceability**. If retailers decide to **put pressure on suppliers**, they can raise environmental standards, socio-economic standards and trigger important leverages for change. **Public governance** should also change. No way we can achieve a transition towards SFS if we spend 1/3 of the EU budget to support industrial food systems.

All actors should be involved and drive the change. However, one of the **"forgotten" but important** are the input of **industry** and the **processing/retail**.

Over the past ten years efforts to drive change in the supply chains have been driven by **industry or by other supply chain actors**. This has also included actions aimed at enhancing sustainability in the supply chains. For me, it seems to remain the key motor to drive change and to make sure that there is no discrepancy between demand and supply. This can be **supported through appropriate policies, a conducive regulatory framework, incentives, promotion at EU level but also beyond**. If the vision we are developing in Europe does not find any similar interest in other parts of the world, it will slow down the process, prevent any **level playing field** for both exporters and importers. This means there needs to be engagement from public authorities to accompany such processes.

Consumers need to become the real drivers, but this requires more transparency and willingness for informed food choices. Regulatory frameworks may need to address this and for any product to be placed on the market, **fuller information on the true cost** of the food along the FVC made available for truly informed choice to be made on basis of validated and accessible information (data).

ANNEX 3: WORKSHOP #3 SLIDO RESULTS

Workshop Conclusions (1/3)

0 1 3

What has been the most surprising and/or valuable result of this workshop series?

(1/2)

- New perspectives towards the transition of more sustainable FVCs
- A certain convergence on the challenges to design the pathway and struggle to take it forward concretely.
- Need to set common standards and KPIs to set the pathway; Need for a new paradigm shift to convince «consumers to pay more for eating less, because it is better for their health...»; CAP should be strengthen the food and dietary policy dimension.
- We are already working on "sustainable solutions" within the food system, maybe only on small scale and only on regional level, but surely with an impact and a benefit for related partners.
- that the dairy value chain is in such a focus regarding sustainability
- The importance of working together with different actors and levels.
- good discussion in breakrooms with high level policy makers and industry representatives very interesting to read the 2-pages stories
- degree of convergence on key challenges across participants
- The recognition of the importance of efforts asked to farmers (usually undermined)
- Sharing our views and learn from each other
- Global need of change in our food system: how to bring consumers to this point?
- food system change / policies
- The dialogue, the people

Workshop Conclusions (2/3)

0 1 4

Do you believe more/less in the value of food systems dialogue coming out of this workshop series (rate 0-5)?

Score: 3.9

Workshop Conclusions (3/3)

0 1 2

... and why?
(1/3)

- the diversity of actors makes it possible to take valuable input
- Dialog always useful to understand the thinking/ideas of other stakeholders
- The visions of different actors on achieving a system change and how, are often far apart and a discussion can help a sort of reality check which can be beneficial for all
- Need to set concrete recommendations agreed upon among stakeholders
- Even though we might see many "sustainability changes" already developed on the markets, I believe the momentum needs to be increased. We need a "new deal" in the sense a societal agreement on sustainability as a major issue for all action in the next decades.
- dialog is the starting point for change
- This workshop is a good starting point. During the workshops it becomes clear

that there are so many topics and actors concerned. On all these different topics so many things are done yet and so many actors are involved. The discussion must be continued on lots of other places.

- There is definitely a need of gathering so many different stakeholders. Nevertheless, some parts of the workshop led

in the process and own together the objective

- Excellent organisation and fruitful discussions

to very "general" and "theoretical" recommendations (in French: "y'a qu'à... faut qu'on...", sometimes "quick win proposals" were lacking.

- So many aspects, angles and approaches needed for food system transformation
- Provides a relatively neutral space - including for our colleagues from the Commission DGs.
- Because discussing together allows to feel more included